

Inventory of U.S. Greenhouse Gas Emissions and Sinks:

1990 – 2014

APRIL 15, 2016

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All data tables of this document are available for the full time series 1990 through 2014, inclusive, at the internet site mentioned above.

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For more information regarding climate change and greenhouse gas emissions, see the EPA web site at <http://www3.epa.gov/climatechange>.

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Preface

The United States Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) prepares the official U.S. Inventory of Greenhouse Gas Emissions and Sinks to comply with existing commitments under the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC). Under decision 3/CP.5 of the UNFCCC Conference of the Parties, national inventories for UNFCCC Annex I parties should be provided to the UNFCCC Secretariat each year by April 15.

In an effort to engage the public and researchers across the country, the EPA has instituted an annual public review and comment process for this document. The availability of the draft document is announced via Federal Register Notice and is posted on the EPA web site. Copies are also mailed upon request. The public comment period is generally limited to 30 days; however, comments received after the closure of the public comment period are accepted and considered for the next edition of this annual report.